

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

GERMANISMS IN THE PROCESS OF LOANWORD IN ENGLISH

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Abstract

When we talk about loanwords, we should consider external factors, which include various influences from other languages that are evident in the graphic, phonetic, lexical, semantic, morphological, and syntactic aspects of language elements. This process takes place as a result of the interaction of related and unrelated languages in both direct and indirect contact, along with continuous improvements based on their internal capabilities and resources.

The key conditions for acquiring new words in a language involves the phonetic and graphic compatibility of borrowed words in the spoken language; associating these borrowed words with grammatical categories in the spoken language; phonetic acquisition of borrowed words; grammatical integration of borrowed words; the significant role of borrowed words in word creation; the semantic acquisition of borrowed words.

Language interaction leads to the borrowing of certain linguistic elements and units between languages. As a result of this process, a word or term is transferred from one language to another. At this time, if borrowing, in other words, a new concept or things is created in response to the needs of the society, and this process of borrowing is typically carried out through the language that adopts the new word. Both English and German belong to the Germanic language group of the Indo-European language family. Modern English contains layers borrowed from various languages, along with lexical units taken from German. The article explores the influence of German borrowings in English.

Keywords: germanisms, borrowing, loanword, word creation, English, language.

There is an excessive amount of literature in modern linguistics that focuses on the role and significance of vocabulary, which is one of the most interesting means of enriching the vocabulary of any language. When we carefully study the modern English language and its various forms, we witness a substantial number of lexical units that have been transferred from other languages. Latin, Greek, French, German borrowings have gained a permanent place in the English lexicon. Since German and English belong to the same language family, they have historically maintained close contact and have exchanged words. However, there are still very few detailed studies examining the interaction between the lexical and semantic systems of English and German. As a result, German loanwords are generally not found in the works that study the etymological composition of the English dictionary.

Several linguists have explained the reasons why loanwords hold a permanent place in the vocabulary of the language from various aspects. H. Hasanov properly categorized these reasons scientifically and theoretically as follows: «1) compliance with the grammatical categories of the mother tongue (recipient language); 2) transforming the mother tongue into a center for new word creation; 3) creating new meanings by combining with native words or becoming independent in meaning; 4) possessing stylistic shades; and 5) combination with the structure of the native language» [7, p.22]. In linguistics, words borrowed from other languages are commonly referred to a term "loanwords", that usually enter a given language in two primary ways: as a result of the crossing of languages and as a result of cultural, historical, socio-economic and other relations of peoples. Thus, for example, throughout its

historical development, the English language has interacted with the Scandinavian languages and the Norman dialect of the French. Furthermore, English has consistently interacted with Latin, French, Spanish, Russian, German, and other languages of the world, leading to linguistic contact.

Borrowings in any language arise from various factors determined by the needs of the development of the lexical-semantic system of the language, as well as the interaction and penetration of languages and cultures. It is well-known that loanwords constitute more than two-thirds of the vocabulary of the English language, with words from primarily derived from Latin, French, and German being the most prevalent. The diverse sources of these words that have entered the English language can be attributed to several historical events. Over the centuries, Britain entered into linguistic contact with many countries, was subject to invasions and occupations, pursued colonial policy, and conducted extensive trade. [11, p.22; 3, p. 126].

The transfer of linguistic phenomena from one language to another is logically considered one of the oldest processes of interlinguistic interaction. At the modern stage of language development, various types of borrowings and calques create a vocabulary that addresses to objective reality and directly reflects events occurring within it. The process of vocabulary is a key method of enriching vocabulary, which is the most dynamic linguistic component of any language, in the process of constant change.

The process of word acquisition, which is one of the processes of word creation in English, is one of the most relevant issues. The relevance of the research is determined by the need to identify the influence of the German language on the English language, particularly

as a result of cross-cultural contacts caused by historical factors, as well as the recent trend of an increasing number of German borrowings being used in the press. Although, the words borrowed from Latin and French languages are well-documented in the scientific literature, despite the abundance of Germanisms in English, they are considered to be less studied areas.

To study Germanisms in modern English, it is essential to carry out these tasks in sequence:

1) the characteristics of the historical context of interaction between the studied languages should be explored; 2) the characteristics of the process of acquisition and assimilation of Germanisms in English should be identified; 3) the semantic areas of Germanisms should be determined; 4) the stylistic potential of borrowed lexemes in contemporary English should be studied.

It is important to consider the historical context for studying the Germanisms used in English word formation. The earliest words borrowed from the German language primarily related to trade, military matters and botany date back to the XVI century. For instance, the word "halt" meaning "Stop!", and "lance-knight" referring to a "knight, armed with a spear" are the examples of these early Germanisms in English.

In the XVII century, the development of mining and metallurgy in Britain led to the active borrowing of German mining terms: *zinc* - sink, *bismut* - wismut, *cobalt* - cobalt, *wolfram* - wolfram, *nickel* - nickel, *gletscher* - glacier [8].

In the XVIII century, the influence of the German language weakened due to the general political and economic deterioration of Germany following the Thirty Years' War.

Since the XIX century, in the process of acquiring words from the German language, there was a notable predominance of lexical units related to the humanities.

Thus, many modern linguistic terms are calques of German words: the terms "folk etymology" was derived from the German word "Volksetymologie", "loanword" came from the word "Lehnwort", borrowed word, and "Indo-Germanic" was adapted from the word "Indogermanische", the lexical unit "umlaut" referring to "the change of vowels" was based on the German word "Umlaut," while the word "ablaut" which signifies the replacement of vowels originated from the same language and they were created as a result of the process of word acquisition.

In addition, German words for household items, food, and drink appeared in English during this period: for example, marzipan – marzipan (almond paste), kohlrabi – kohlrabi (turnip greens), schnapps – liquor, kirsch - cherry, wermut - vermouth, etc.

At the same time, during this period, the German language emerged as a significance source of musical terminology, largely due to the immense contributions of German and Austrian composers to the development of world music culture. [1, p. 66]. As a result, the musical terminology system of the English language includes a considerable number of German words. For example:

"abendmusik" - evening concert in the church, "alpenhorn" - shepherd's pipe (was used to call cattle),

"flugelhorn" – a type of wind instrument (brass musical instrument), "nachtmusik" - serenade, "sprechgesang" – chanting (a style of singing that combines speaking and singing), "walzer" - waltz, etc.

The XX century is characterized by the introduction of German military terms into the lexicology of the English language. For instance, "gauleiter" – "gauleiter" (a regional leader in Nazi Germany), "Sturmabteilung" translated as "stormtroopers" referring to members of the assault team, attacker, "blitzkrieg" – "blitzkrieg" in the meaning "lightning war", a rapid and intense military campaign, "bunker" – "bunker" (shelter), "Luftwaffe" – "Luftwaffe" (the air force of Nazi Germany), "Wehrmacht" – "wehrmacht" (the unified armed forces of Nazi Germany).

Of course, such class of German loanwords in English emerged largely in connection with the First and Second World Wars.

In contemporary English, these borrowed words are often associated with specific historical periods [6, p.23]. When examining German words in English from a historical point of view, we find out that the majority of them are titles and names of government bodies. For example, the word "kaiser" - "kaiser" refers to emperor, "burggraf" means "burgrave" (a type of noble, duke), "landgraf" translates to "landgrave" (landowner), "burgher" - "burgher" denotes a citizen of a town or city, typically from a wealthy family in Western Europe), "Junker" - "Junker" refers to a military school student, and "Rathaus" means "town hall or city hall". These terms represent names and political terms.

Some lexical units have changed their semantics over time. For instance, the German word "lebensraum", which is translated to "living space", was originally introduced in the late XIX century and was reinterpreted by the Nazi movement. Additionally, the German term "putsch", which means "an attempted coup d'état", has also been adopted into English.

As the natural sciences advanced in Germany, many terms related to mineralogy were adopted from the German language to English. Here are some examples: the term "cobalt" remains "cobalt" in both languages, referring to the chemical element, "feldspat" known in English as "feldspath/feldspar", mineral belonging to the group of silicates, "hornblende" describes dark green or black-brown, opaque mineral with a glass luster, consisted of silicates of calcium, magnesium, and iron, "meerscham" – a lightweight, refractory mineral, "quarz" in English is called "quartz", "aurochs" refers to the wild ox the name of which derived from German word "aurochse", "gemsbok" refers to a type of antelope known as "gemsbok" (ox) – a breed belonging to the cloven-hoofed family of the group of ungulates, a "hamster" – "hamster" (a mountain mouse) is the same in both languages, "der dachshund" – "a dachshund" (a small dog with a long body and short legs), "pudel" translates to "poodle" (a dog with curly coat), "schnauzer" – "schnauzer" refers to a medium- or small-sized dog of German origin with a close, wiry coat and heavy whiskers round the muzzle, "lärche" refers to "larch", a tall tree grown in cold northern countries and has needle-like leaves that it loses in winter), "linden" – "a lime tree", a perennial perennial plant

with yellowish-white flowers that grows in the Alps, “das polster” translates to “cushion plant”, “der bast” means “fiber”, etc.

The vocabulary of the English language includes German terms that are used in everyday life. For example, culinary lexicon: “bratwurst” - “bratwurst” (German name for sausage), “sauerkraut” from “das kraut”, meaning sour cabbage, “die torte” in the meaning “cake”, “nudel” in the meaning of “noodle or pasta”, “brezel” in the meaning “pretzel” (a crisp biscuit baked in the form of a knot or stick and flavoured with salt); sports lexicon: “abseiling” from “abseil”, the sport or activity of descending a rock, mountaineers, “alpenstock” from “wanderstock”, an iron-tipped hand pole for climbing high mountains, “kegler” in the meaning “bowler” (kegler player – a person who bowls), “langlauf” in the meaning of “cross-country skiing”, “schnorcheln” in the meaning “snorkel”, a short tube for a swimmer to breathe through while keeping their face under water.

The process of assimilation of German words into English has been facilitated by the genetic similarities in the phonetics, grammar and lexical composition between two languages. During the research, we witnessed that the share of completely assimilated units in the total number of Germanisms reaches 70%, for example, terms such as “abseil” (the activity of descending a rock), “snorkel” (a short tube for a swimmer to breathe under water), and “wunderkind” – “wonderkid” (a child with exceptional abilities, a child prodigy) [5, p. 108] are now commonly used in English.

The partially assimilated words from the German language make up for about 15% of the vocabulary, for example: “glockenspiele” – “glockenspiel” refers to a type of metallophone - a percussion instrument with chromatically tuned, flat metal bars set in a frame, producing bell-like tones when struck with small hammers.), “kindergärten” – “kindergarten”, “schadenfreude” - “schadenfreude” (malice, which means taking pleasure in someone else’s misfortune).

15% of the researched material consists of unassimilable loanwords, such as “blockflöte” which means “vertical flute” and “das singspiel” – “singspiel” (musical comedy or light opera). Thus, the majority of Germanisms are not recognized by English speakers as words of foreign origin.

Let’s take a closer look at the assimilation process. Thus, the verb “abseilen” in German refers to descending on a rope. The separable prefix “ab” means “down”, and it comes from the noun “das Seil” which means “rope” [4]. Since this sport originated in the Alps in German-speaking areas, the verb is commonly associated with the term “climbing”. According to the Oxford English Dictionary [9], the verb “abseil” was adopted into English in the 1930s and has since been completely assimilated both morphologically and grammatically: *From rock climbing to hot-air ballooning or abseiling down underground waterfalls – pick a university that lets you indulge your love of the great outdoors.*

The German word “kindergärten”, which entered the English language in the early XIX century, was partially assimilated. The concept of “kindergarten” was proposed by the German educator F. Froebel in 1837,

who believed that children are like the flowers of life and require skillful and careful care, and should be raised by gardeners. It is interesting that, this concept was integrated into both Russian and Azerbaijani languages through the method known as calque word creation.

The German word “*kindergarten*” has been quickly incorporated into the English language due to the close connection between the two languages, especially at the morphological and grammatical levels [5, p. 101]. While the last stage of assimilation of the word “*kindergarten*” at the phonetic level has not yet been recorded officially in dictionaries, but it has begun to appear in journalistic texts:

Of Puerto Rican decent, she was born in the Bronx to a computer programmer and a kindergarten teacher [The Guardian. 2016. 16 May.15].

German loanwords in English have different stylistic meanings, but according to our observations, a significant number of these Germanisms have an emotional function and are characterized by social marking, as well as low frequency in spoken language. For example, “angst” refers to “fear or anxiety”, “doppelgänger” – “doppelganger” denotes a mysterious, exact double of a living person who is not a twin, “schadenfreude” - “schadenfreude” describes maliciousness, the pleasure derived by someone from another person's misfortune, “wanderlust” - “wanderlust” expresses a strong desire to travel.

It is more appropriate to demonstrate the stylistic potential of German expressions with examples from contemporary journalism. Thus, the German word “schadenfreude” (maliciousness), which according to the Collins Dictionary means taking pleasure in someone else's misfortune [2], frequently appears in media reports.

Unlike most other Germanisms, this noun is capitalized in English texts: May's PMQs disaster gives Cameron parting gift of Schadenfreude [The Guardian. 2016. 5 September]

According to the Collins Dictionary, the German word Angst, means “*an acute but nonspecific sense of anxiety or remorse*” [2], first entered the English language through the translations of the works of S. Freud and S. Kierkegaard.

This lexeme is stylistically colorful and is used in journalism to empower: *Rashid and Hales have somehow heightened the existential angst surrounding cricket's future* [The Guardian. 2018. 28 October.]

The term “Spiel”, which originates from German language, has acquired negative stylistic semantics over time as a result of semantic development in the process of word acquisition, and in contemporary English, according to the Collins Dictionary, it refers to a “*style of talk, speech associated with salespeople*” [2]. The popularity of German literature of the Romantic era contributed to the adoption of the German word “*Doppelgänger*”, which describes the resemblance of the character who represents the dark sides of personality, acting as an antithesis to a guardian angel.

In contemporary English, this Germanism in addition to its literary significance, according to the Collins Dictionary, it refers to a meaning “ghostly associated

with a living person” or someone who resembles, looks exactly like another person but is not related to him” [2].

The research identified specific regularities in the distribution of loanwords according to the parts of speech. The main group of Germanisms consists of nouns, making up 90.5% of the total. This is natural. First of all, new objects and events typically require names. In general, it would be reasonable to state that the majority of word creation involves nouns.

Germanisms that take the form of other parts of speech are relatively uncommon in English.

Adjectives such as “*aufregen*” – “exciting”, “*echte*” – “real, true”, “*glitzernde*” – “glitzy, bright, attractive”, “*wanderlust*” – “strong desire to explore the world” make up 5% of the material.

Less frequently used derivative verbs include such words as “*spielen*” – “game, to gamble”, “*hält*” – “to stop”, “*strafe*” – “punishment, penalty, to penalise”. Germanisms consisting of verbs make up 3% of the material.

The smallest percentage, at 1.5%, consists of adverbs, such as “*geistlich*” meaning “*spiritually*”. It is noteworthy that there are also exclamations among the Germanisms, like the “*wish for health*” (expression stated when sneezing, etc.) derived from the noun “*gesundheit*” (health).

Not only words, but also productive affixes that are actively involved in word formation are incorporated into English, for example, “burger” leads to “cheeseburger” and “hamburger”, the suffix “fest” contributes to terms such as “feast (festival)”, “snoozefest” (a term for boring event), “talkfest” (conversation, a discussion or debate on a matter of public concern), the suffix “meister” is found in words like “meister” (master), “webmeister” which refers to a “webmaster”.

In the last case, we notice that ironic professional titles are created. Consequently, it can be noted that the suffixes –“fest” and –“meister” have acquired an evaluative meaning.

The penetration of German words into the English language can be evaluated as a reflection of the globalization at the lexical level. It should be noted that, there is a noticeable process of acquiring more active words in the opposite direction, that is, from English to German [12; 13]. Overall, it can be noted that media texts tend to include more neologisms and borrowed words to express new political, scientific, cultural, or economic realities compared to other types of writing. In media discourse, these borrowed words mainly acquire evaluative and expressive meanings.

Azerbaijani linguist T. Ismayilova explains the recent intensification of acquisitions in the language with advancements in information technology. The scientist states: “In the civilized world, the XXI century is characterized as the information age. In this context, the integration of peoples and nations, the opening of borders, the rapid exchange of information, and the rise of Scientific and Technical Progress (STP) indicate that those nations and languages will endure in history, behind which there is a strong economy. While languages that do not connect with one another will become isolated and eventually disappear from history. Taking into

account this real historical reality, it is essential to emphasize the relevance of the issue of loanwords, particularly at this time when it is crucial to prevent the suppression of the native elements of the language [10, p.133].

Conclusion. The presence of a significant number of Germanisms in the terminological systems of the English language is explained by Germany's leading role in various fields of science, classical music, art, philosophy, literature, military, and sports. The easy assimilation of German words into English can be attributed to the genetic affiliation of these languages to the same language group and the common cultural heritage of their speakers. One of the indicators of the active assimilation process of Germanisms is their involvement in the creation of new words. Generally, the stylistic potential of lexemes obtained from German in modern English usually acts as an indicator of the speaker's high social status and educational level, particularly for terms belonging to the fields of terminology, science, literature, and philosophy.

Consequently, German loanwords are actively used in modern English. The penetration of Germanisms into the English language began in the XVI century and continues up today with varying intensity. The significant impact of the German language on the English is the result of active cultural exchanges between these peoples through both direct and indirect (scientific, literary) language contacts.

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